

Simulation of Detecting 1-D Motion of Transparent Cylindrical Grains using Narrow Laser Beam

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Abstract. Motion in 1-D of a transparent cylindrical grain (TCG) is detected using a narrow laser beam. Several light sensors are placed in several positions across the light source. Propagation of light is modeled based only on Snell's law and neglecting the intensity reduction due to reflection as described in Fresnel equations. Response of light sensor is only 0 (without incident light on the sensor) and 1 (with incident light on the sensor). An attempt of digitizing the information from eight sensor into number is also presented, which is more compact while representing the measurement result in a time series. When several grains moving in sequence the results could be different and must be interpreted carefully.

INTRODUCTION

Ray tracing is still an interesting subject to study [1], especially when apparatus configuration is the limitation [2]. Flow or motion of single grain can be detected through magnetic induction in uniform straight motion [3], uniform circular motion [4], or several bouncing-back motion [5]. A thought experiment system with gravitation has also been discussed [6]. In this work position of a transparent cylindrical grain (TGC) is detected by observing the laser deflected by the grain as it is moving through the measurement system, which is detected by light sensor.

THEORY

Supposed there is a cylindrical grain i with diameter D_i moving in x direction with velocity v_i passing a channel with a width of w and length of l as shown in Figure 1. Grain z axis is parallel to z axis of the system.

Figure 1. Measurement system for detection 1-d motion of a cylindrical transparent grain.

There are M light sensors, where sensor j is located at

$$x_j = \left(j - \frac{1}{2} \right) \frac{l}{M} \quad (1)$$

and $y_j = 0.5 w$. Each sensor gives value of 0 without incident light and 1 with incident light. Condition in Figure 1 gives value of 0 for all sensors. This zero reading for all sensors happens when

$$x_i \leq -\frac{1}{2} D_i \cup x_i = 0 \cup x_i \geq \frac{1}{2} D_i \quad (2)$$

as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Condition of zero reading for all sensor.

A non-zero reading happens when

$$-\frac{1}{2} D_i < x_i < 0 \cup 0 < x_i < \frac{1}{2} D_i. \quad (3)$$

A condition for $-D_i/2 < x_i < 0$ is illustrated in Figure 3 and condition for $0 < x_i < D_i/2$ will be similar.

Figure 3. Condition for $-D_i/2 < x_i < 0$ with refractive index $n_i > 1$.

Using (x_s, y_s) and circle equation representing TCG i

$$(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2 = \frac{1}{4} D_i^2, \quad (4)$$

with $x_{in} = x_s$ it can be obtained that

$$y_{in} = y_i - \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}D_i^2 - (x_{in} - x_i)^2}, \quad (5)$$

by choosing the solution that less than y_i as shown in Figure 3. From (x_s, y_s) and (x_{in}, y_{in}) unit vector of incident light can be constructed

$$\hat{i} = \frac{(x_{in} - x_s)\hat{x} + (y_{in} - y_s)\hat{y}}{\sqrt{(x_{in} - x_s)^2 + (y_{in} - y_s)^2}}, \quad (6)$$

and also the normal vector between two media

$$\hat{n} = \frac{(x_{in} - x_i)\hat{x} + (y_{in} - y_i)\hat{y}}{\sqrt{(x_{in} - x_i)^2 + (y_{in} - y_i)^2}}. \quad (7)$$

Vector of refracted light \hat{r} can be built from

$$\hat{r} = \hat{n} \cos \theta_r + (\hat{n} \times \hat{z}) \sin \theta_r, \quad (8)$$

which requires the information about θ_r . Snell's law

$$\frac{\sin \theta_i}{n_i} = \sin \theta_r, \quad (9)$$

relates incident angle θ_i and refracted angle θ_r . Equations (6) and (7) will give

$$\cos \theta_i = -\hat{i} \cdot \hat{n} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\cos \theta_r = -\hat{r} \cdot \hat{n}. \quad (11)$$

From Equations (9) and (10) following relations can be obtained

$$\cos \theta_r = \sqrt{1 - \left[\frac{1}{n_i} \sqrt{1 - (\hat{i} \cdot \hat{n})^2} \right]^2} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\sin \theta_r = \left[\frac{1}{n_i} \sqrt{1 - (\hat{i} \cdot \hat{n})^2} \right]. \quad (13)$$

Substitute Equations (11) and (12) into Equation (8) will give

$$\hat{r} = \hat{n} \sqrt{1 - \left[\frac{1}{n_i} \sqrt{1 - (\hat{i} \cdot \hat{n})^2} \right]^2} + (\hat{n} \times \hat{z}) \left[\frac{1}{n_i} \sqrt{1 - (\hat{i} \cdot \hat{n})^2} \right]. \quad (14)$$

Light beam from (x_{in}, y_{in}) can be constructed using

$$\tan \theta_{in} = \frac{\hat{r} \cdot \hat{y}}{\hat{r} \cdot \hat{x}} \quad (15)$$

that produces

$$y = \tan \theta_{in} (x - x_{in}) + y_{in} \quad (16)$$

or

$$x = \cot \theta_{in} (y - y_{in}) + x_{in}. \quad (17)$$

Substitute Equations (16) and (17) into Equation (4) will give

$$[\cot \theta_{in} (y - y_{in}) + x_{in} - x_i]^2 + [\tan \theta_{in} (x - x_{in}) + y_{in} - y_i]^2 = \frac{1}{4} D_i^2. \quad (18)$$

If (x_{in}, y_{in}) is inserted into Equation (18) relation of $(x_{in} - x_i)^2 + (y_{in} - y_i)^2 = \frac{1}{4}D_i^2$ will be produced, which is one of the solution and (x_{out}, y_{out}) is the other solution

$$[\cot \theta_{in} (y_{out} - y_{in}) + x_{in} - x_i]^2 + [\tan \theta_{in} (x_{out} - x_{in}) + y_{in} - y_i]^2 = \frac{1}{4}D_i^2. \quad (19)$$

Equation (19) could be solved iteratively, e.g. fixed point method. The other way to find (x_{out}, y_{out}) is using vector analysis. From Figure 3 it can be written that

$$\frac{1}{2}D_i \hat{n} + l_c \hat{r} = \frac{1}{2}D_i \hat{n}', \quad (20)$$

where

$$\hat{n}' = \frac{(x_{out} - x_i)\hat{x} + (y_{out} - y_i)\hat{y}}{\sqrt{(x_{out} - x_i)^2 + (y_{out} - y_i)^2}} \quad (21)$$

and l_c is chord length. From Equation (20) there are two unknown, which are l_c and \hat{n}' . Since there is Equation (11) and the isosceles triangle made of (x_{in}, y_{in}) , (x_i, y_i) , and (x_{out}, y_{out}) , angle between two radii β can be determined.

Figure 4. Isosceles triangle made of (x_{in}, y_{in}) , (x_i, y_i) , and (x_{out}, y_{out}) .

$$\beta = \pi - 2\text{acos}(-\hat{r} \cdot \hat{n}). \quad (22)$$

From sine law

$$\frac{\sin \theta_r}{\frac{1}{2}D_i} = \frac{\sin \beta}{l_c}, \quad (23)$$

which leads to

$$l_c = \frac{D_i \sin[2\text{acos}(-\hat{r} \cdot \hat{n})]}{2 \sin \theta_r}. \quad (24)$$

Then

$$(x_{out}\hat{x} + y_{out}\hat{y}) = (x_{in}\hat{x} + y_{in}\hat{y}) + \frac{1}{2}D_i\hat{n} + l_c\hat{r}, \quad (25)$$

or

$$x_{out} = x_{in} + \left(\frac{1}{2}D_i\hat{n} + l_c\hat{r}\right) \cdot \hat{x}, \quad (26)$$

and

$$y_{out} = y_{in} + \left(\frac{1}{2}D_i\hat{n} + l_c\hat{r}\right) \cdot \hat{y}. \quad (27)$$

After finding (x_{out}, y_{out}) and use of \hat{n}'

$$\sin \theta_r' = n_i \sin \theta_i' \quad (28)$$

with

$$\cos \theta_i' = \hat{i}' \cdot \hat{n}' = \hat{r} \cdot \hat{n}' \equiv \cos \theta_r. \quad (29)$$

The last term in Equation (29) is due to property of isoscales triangle. After obtaining refracted angle outside the TCG from Equation (29) the unit vector of refracted beam is

$$\hat{r}' = \hat{n}' \cos \theta_r' + (\hat{z} \times \hat{n}') \sin \theta_r' = \hat{n}'(\hat{i}' \cdot \hat{n}') + (\hat{z} \times \hat{n}') \sqrt{1 - (\hat{i}' \cdot \hat{n}')^2}. \quad (30)$$

And similar to Equation (15)

$$\tan \theta_{\text{out}} = \frac{\hat{r}' \cdot \hat{y}}{\hat{r}' \cdot \hat{x}} \quad (31)$$

that produces

$$y = \tan \theta_{\text{out}} (x - x_{\text{out}}) + y_{\text{out}}. \quad (32)$$

By setting value of $y = w/2$ position of sensor j can be found

$$j = 1 + \left\lfloor \frac{x_{\text{out}} + \cot \theta_{\text{out}} (y - y_{\text{out}})}{l/M} \right\rfloor. \quad (33)$$

From Equation (33) it can be determined which sensor has value of 0 and which one of 1. Binary number produced by the sensor array will be

$$(B)_2 = (00000001)_2 \ll (j - 1), \quad (34)$$

where \ll is symbol for logical shift. And decimal conversion will be simply

$$b_j = [(B)_2 \wedge 2^{(j-1)}] \gg (j - 1) \quad (35)$$

and followed by

$$(D)_{10} = \sum_{j=1}^8 b_j 2^{b_j}. \quad (36)$$

But since only one sensor has reading value of 1 at a time, Equation (36) can be simplified into

$$(D)_{10} = 2^{(j-1)}. \quad (37)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simulation has been performed with a JavaScript code in the `simlittcg.html` file (source is available at [Github]), whose snapshot of the application is given in following Figure 5.

Figure 5. Application `simlittcg.html` for the simulation with parts are: time series data (TSD), sensor array (SA), transparent cylindrical grain (TCG), start-stop button (SSB), step-left button (SLB), step-right button (SRB), laser source (LS), and laser beam (SB).

Reading result of sensor array for condition in Figure 5 is 00001000_2 or 8_{10} .

Figure 6. Typical bending of laser beam the cylindrical transparent grain passing the system.

Figure 6 first row will give result of SA in the form of 00000000 , second row 00100000 , third row 00000000 , and fourth row 00000100 , which can reconstructed to find particle velocity and vertical position when compared to periode of SA reading process.

Variation of particle distance to the SA will affect sensor reading, where the results for three different distance is given in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Influence of TGC vertical distance to SA in producing the reading: near (top), middling (middle), and far (bottom) from the sensor.

From Figure 7 it can be seen that particle distance to SA does have influence to the reading, where some sensors could not fire a signal when the TGC is too close to the sensors, e.g. 1 (gives value of 1) and 7 (gives value of 32) will not be active. Value of 0 (all sensors are not active) in the middle of the reading shows that the TGC passes the center of the system.

CONCLUSION

Simulation of system of detecting 1-d motion of cylindrical transparent grains using narrow laser beam has been built. Sensor reading is still hard to be formulated for representing the physical result if it is so constructed in hardware as assumed, especially when observed object does not move parallel to the channel wall. Object position will influence the results differently with different distance to the sensors.

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